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Research Article

**QUANTIFY THE PRESSURE OF RECENTLY REPORTED
CASES OF DOG BITE IN THE LAHORE TERTIARY CARE
CENTER AND TO EVALUATE THE CONSCIOUSNESS OF
THESE PATIENTS**¹Dr Amna Javaid, ²Dr Ramsha Khalid, ³Dr Afra Ahmad¹Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi, ²Nishter Hospital Multan, ³Mayo Hospital Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: To estimate the burden of recently reported cases of dog bite in a tertiary care center of Lahore and to analyze the awareness of these victims or their attendants about dog bite.

Methods: This cross sectional study was conducted during Mayo Hospital Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. Our sample was comprised of 393 patients, reporting first time after stray dog bite incident. The relevant information was obtained regarding patients' age, gender, details of injury, management and patients' knowledge about dog bite and rabies. SPSS 13 was used to manage data and perform analysis.

Results: It was found that 83% of the victims were males and 52.4% were of less than 15 years of age. In our data, 26.7% victims reported within twenty-four hours of the dog bite. Mapping of dog bite cases revealed that 24% belonged to Orange town while 14% each from North Lahore and Nazimabad. Knowledge of people related to rabies was very poor and 91% did not know that rabies could result after dog bite. Only 7% knew that rabies is a fatal disease and 0.7% responded that it can be prevented by vaccines.

Conclusion:

Dog bite is a significant public health problem among young males with preponderance in certain areas of Lahore. Lack of education of people and lack of health communication reflected well through carefree practices and attitude of victims of dog bite.

Keywords: Dog Bite, Lahore Tertiary Care Center.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Amna Javaid,**

Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi.

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INTRODUCTION:

Rabies is a disease of immense public health importance in developing countries where scanty and ineffective measures are adopted to control the infection both in animals and in humans. A World Health Organization (WHO) rabies survey in 1992 estimated that 90% of human rabies occur in the developing world. All carnivorous animals, including dogs, cats, jackals, mongooses and raccoons are considered potentially as rabid and transmit infection to humans [1]. Whereas rodents like mice though not rabid but may harbor the infection and spread it through bite. Although it is an uncommon infection, the disease is uniformly fatal and ends in an extremely painful and torturous death if it becomes symptomatic. Globally, the incidence of human rabies is very low and virtually Europe, North America and Australia are declared to be free of human rabies [2]. Rabies is endemic in the Asia Pacific region while local epidemics are not uncommon. In India, the annual incidence of dog bite is 1.9%. Of all the deaths reported due to rabies each year, 95% occur in Asia and Africa and India alone accounts for 60% of all the world burden of rabies-related deaths. According to a study carried out in India, the Bangalore city has an estimated dog population of lakhs while the density of dogs was reported as 6-10 dogs per km² in Jaipur and Mumbai. The incidence of rabies was more in males and mostly (64%) resulted from stray dogs. About 86% of them received anti-rabies vaccination and none received lifesaving Anti-Rabies Serum (ARS). The annual incidence of human rabies reported was 15 and dog rabies 58 resulting in a ratio of 1:4 approximately as a rabies contagion index [3]. Annually 55,000 deaths due to rabies have been reported in Asia & Africa. Unfortunately, no formal statistics are available regarding the burden of dog bite in our local population. According to some popular press releases, 7000 cases of dog bites are managed every year in JPMC. Moreover, the veterinary services are barely monitored to show the extent of the problem in the community. Only a few studies have been carried out to evaluate the compliance of post-exposure treatment and barely a couple of case reports are published [4]. All over the developed world, research is being done to control canine rabies by newer vaccines but because of a lack of veterinary services and administrative constraints we are way behind. This study is taken up as an initial effort to spotlight the burden of animal bite and people's awareness towards control of rabies. According to projected estimates, dog population in metropolitan city of Lahore is 1.1 lakh (dog to human ratio is 1:145) and pet to stray dog's ratio is 1:100. Therefore, in a city of more than 20 million people, almost 1.1 million are at risk of being bitten by animals and the figures can be

more concentrated for rural-urban areas in the outskirts of Lahore. It would be helpful in raising the awareness of the population at risk about rabies through health communication and directing municipal measures in these potential areas subsequently. This study was carried out in order to analyze epidemiological features of dog bite in Lahore city and also to depict knowledge, attitude and practices of our local population regarding its complications and prevention [5].

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted during Mayo Hospital Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. This project was carried out in collaboration of Community Medicine and Emergency department of KMDC & ASH. Mayo Hospital, Lahore is a public sector tertiary care hospital catering to a large population of approximately five to six million as its catchment area. Our sample was comprised of all those patients reporting first time to ASH with recent dog bite incident during that period. The study sample comprised of three hundred and ninety-three (393) subjects irrespective of age and gender who reported directly or referred to emergency department at ASH. The relevant information including patients' age, gender, details of injury, management and patients' knowledge about manifestations and complications of rabies were recorded through a pre-designed questionnaire. The questionnaire was pilot tested among a few lay persons, prior to the initiation of the actual study. Data was entered and processed using SPSS 13.00 software. Descriptive analysis was used to calculate the frequency and proportion of age, gender, treatment and management, knowledge and practices of patients, and geographical distribution of dog bite. We used Arc View® software to show the distribution of dog bite incidence of our sample (Fig. 1). Incidence of dog bite is estimated by taking whole population of reported towns in our sample as population at risk. We also calculated individual incidence for each town. All the statistics related to size of population were quoted according to the city district government official website.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the sample (393 cases) was found to be 21.5 ± 17.3 years with 52.4% (206) were less than 15 years, 37.4% (147) adults and 10% (40) cases were elderly; 83% (326) of all the victims were males. Of all the dog bite victims, 26.7% (101/378) reported at Mayo Hospital, Lahore on the same day within twenty-four hours of the bite, while 73.3% reported between 24-48 hours of the incident. Most of the victims 24% belonged to Orange town followed by 14% each from

North Lahore and Nazimabad, 12% each from North Nazimabad and New Lahore while 11% from Federal B area (Fig. 3). It was revealed that 54% (212) of victims were visitors in that area on that particular day of the bite. In this study we estimated the incidence of dog bite for Jan-June 2008 as 7.8 dog bites per one hundred thousand populations in the vicinity of ASH (Fig. 1). It was seen that 59% (231) of the cases were reported in the months of January and February and the common time of injury was late evening and early morning. Most of the victims in our sample sustained single site injuries. Injuries on leg account for 52% of the total cases followed by feet 26% and hand 14.8%. A total of 28 people (7.1%) were having multiple sites of injuries as shown in Table 1. In 83% of the cases first reported at ASH, allegedly gave history of bleeding with bite mark while in 13% only abrasions and 7% only bite mark. We calculated time delay by subtracting the day of bite from day of first reporting to our hospital. We were able to ascertain time delay in 378 out of 393 total reported cases of dog bites. There a delay in days was 1.43 (SE 0.07 days) while median delay was 1 day with a minimum of zero day (same day reporting of incident) and maximum of eight days. It was seen that 80% (317) were not at all aware of any serious consequences of dog bite that is rabies. Whereas 15% (62) thought that wound or local infection was the main problem to be managed by some injectable medicine Fig. 2. Only 3.8% responders said that complications of dog bite can be prevented by vaccines whereas 93.2% showed vague or incomplete

knowledge of preventive measures against dog bite. Knowledge of people was very poor and 91% did not know that rabies is the disease that can result after dog bite. Only 6.9 % knew that it is a fatal disease and 3.6% said that it can spread from animal to human while 0.3% responded that human-to-human transmission is possible Fig. 3. Response rate for attitude towards control measures was only 46% (181/393). It was reflected that though 72% (130/181) noted but only 2% of them notified the authority regarding increased number of stray dogs in their area.

DISCUSSION:

All over the world, males are the predominant victims of dog bite and so in our study with 83% [6]. males in total sample. The possible explanation for this high rate of male preponderance could be more exposure of males to outdoor activities due to our cultural and socioeconomic dependence on males [7-8]. Children are vulnerable habitants particularly in outside environment and high proportion of child victims 52.4% in our sample endorsed this fact and also well supported by other studies [9]. Earlier studies reported that most of the dog bites were on single site Similarly in our data 1193% of bites were of single site injuries with lower extremities as the most common site. It should be appreciated that western studies reported face neck and head as the most common sites of bite whereas, in our study and other local regional studies lower extremity was the most frequent site of bite by stray dog [10].

This could be due to the cultural reasons in Asia region where dogs are mostly kept at a distance and pet dogs within the premises of home are rare finding. It is an observed fact that in western culture both children and adults interact and play with dogs and dogs live along with humans inside the home and have access to the bedrooms also as most of the dog bites are unexpected the site of bite depends mainly on the activity of the victim just prior to the bite. It is a known fact that chances of dog bite are higher in those areas where human dog ratio is high. We found substantial reporting of dog bite from low socioeconomic area like Orangi Town and New Lahore. Reason may be due to the fact these communities have small houses, larger families and lack of recreation facilities especially for children and as a result they tend to play on streets and prone to get exposure to stray dogs. Time of injury commonly reported in our study was late evening and early morning. The explanation of this may be the poor visibility and ideal time for stray dogs on streets. This is different from western studies where the peak incidence is early morning 15-17. Earlier studies have stated higher incidence of dog bite in harvesting season starting from April to September. In our data months of January 11, 20, 21 and February showed higher incidence of dog bite. We may not be able to comment on this occurrence until a data is collected for over a whole year including all seasons. Victims of dog bite having multiple bites were mostly (48%) young males and they gave history of dog bite in past as well. People, who were bitten previously, surprisingly did not get immunization against rabies and yet showed no signs of the disease.

CONCLUSION:

Dog bite is a significant public health problem with high frequency among young males and it was predominant in Orange town area of Lahore. In half of the victims, reporting to tertiary care hospital was delayed for more than 24 hours for varied reasons and bleeding wounds were the commonest ones reported in time. Single site injuries were found to be more frequent. Furthermore, knowledge and attitude of our participants regarding complications and prevention of dog bite was very unsatisfactory. It can be postulated that lack of awareness of people and lack of health communication reflected well through their carefree practices and attitude towards serious problem of dog bite.

REFERENCES:

1. Totton SC1, Wandeler AI, Zinsstag J, Bauch CT, Ribble CS, Rosatte RC, McEwen SA. Stray dog population demographics in Jodhpur, India following a population control/rabies vaccination

- program. *Prev Vet Med.* 2010 Oct 1;97(1):51-7. doi:10.1016/j.prevetmed.2010.07.009. Epub 2010 Aug 8.
2. Sudarshan MK, Mahendra BJ, Narayan DH. A community survey of dog bites, anti-rabies treatment, rabies and dog population management in Bangalore city. *J Com Dis* 2001;33:245-51.
3. Costa P, Briggs JD, Tumpsey A, Dedmon R, Coutts J. World rabies day outreach to Asia: empowering people through education. *Asian Biomed* 2009;3:451-7.10. Ali NS. Guidelines for prophylaxis of rabies in Pakistan. *Pak J Med Sci* 2003;19:61-5. Available from: <http://pjms.com.pk/issues/janmar03/article11.pdf>. Accessed on May, 2014.
4. Parviz S, Luby S, Wilde H. Post exposure treatment of rabies in Pakistan. *Clin Infect Dis* 1998;27:751-6.12. Pervaiz S, Chotani R, McCormick J, Fischer H, Luby S. Rabies deaths in Pakistan: results of in-effective post-exposure treatment. *Int J Infect Dis* 2004;8:346-52.
5. Naseem S, Muniba J. Human Rabies: Experience of eight cases at Liaquat national hospital, Lahore. *Infect Dis J Pak* 2000;9:23-4. <http://www.pakmedinet.com/533>.
6. Ahmad R, Rehman RA. Dog Bite, rabies and vaccination failure. *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak* 2001;11:397-8. Available from: <http://www.pakmedinet.com/896>. Accessed on May, 2014.
7. Fèver EM, Kaboyo RW, Person V, Edelsten M, Coleman PG, Cleveland S. The epidemiology of animal bite injuries in Uganda and projection of the burden of rabies. *Trop Med Int Health* 2005;10:790-8.
8. Krebs JW, Wheeling JT, Childs JE. Rabies surveillance in the United States during 2002. *J Am Vet Med Assoc* 2003;223:1736-48.
9. Vanaga S, van der Heide R, Joffe R, van der Poel WH. Rabies in wildlife in Latvia. *Vector Borne Zoonotic Dis* 2003;3:117-24.
10. Sudarshan MK, Nagaraj S, Savitha B, Veena SG. An epidemiological study of rabies in Bangalore city. *J Indian Med Assoc* 1995;93:146-7.